

Original article

Gastrointestinal cancers in Northeastern Nigeria: a review of demographic and histopathological characteristics

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Abstract

Background: Gastrointestinal tract (GI) cancers are among the most common cancers affecting humans globally. The global incidence and mortality of the disease have demonstrated a significant temporal and geographic variation although the epidemiology and histopathologic characteristics have not been adequately reported among black Africans. In Nigeria, there is poor characterization of the disease due to lack of studies that reflect the epidemiology of the disease. **Objective:** This study aimed to examine the demographic and histopathological characteristics of gastrointestinal cancers in Northeastern Nigeria. **Materials and Methods:** This was a quantitative retrospective analysis of patients diagnosed with gastrointestinal cancers at six tertiary institutions in Northeastern Nigeria from January 2019 to December 2022. We selected six major tertiary referral centers to get diverse and representative data. Patient's information retrieved included age, gender, organ(s) affected, tumor sub-sites, histological diagnosis, and histological sub-type of the tumor. The data collected was analyzed using SPSS version 26 (IBM SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA). **Results:** A total of 579 patients were reviewed, within the age range 2 - 92 years, and a median age of 52 years. The incidence of GI cancers in this study was 16.1% (579/3596). There were 348 (60.1%) males and 231 (39.9%) females, with male-female ratio of 1.5:1. Majority of the patients 441 (76.2%) were 40 years or older. The common sites affected were the colorectal 279 (48.2%), liver 124 (21.4%), stomach 109 (18.8%), small intestine 32 (5.5%), esophagus 26 (4.5%), and pancreas 9 (1.6%). Overall, epithelial cancers (predominantly adenocarcinoma) were the commonest representing about 88.4% of the cases (512/579). All the pancreatic cancers were derived from the pancreatic ducts with 4 of them located at the head of the pancreas, while majority of the esophageal cancers were squamous cell carcinoma 15/26 (57.7%). **Conclusion:** The incidence of GI cancers in Northeastern Nigeria was 16.1%. The incidence is increasing with age, with a male preponderance. The most common site affected was the colorectal region, followed by the liver and stomach. The colorectal adenocarcinoma, gastric adenocarcinoma, and hepatocellular carcinoma are the most common histological subtypes.

Keywords: Gastrointestinal cancers, Histopathology, Demography, Cancer epidemiology, Northeastern Nigeria.

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Introduction

Globally, cancer is a public health problem associated with high morbidity and mortality. It was reported that the incidence and mortality of cancer are increasing from about 14.9 million cases and 8.2 million deaths in the year 2013 to about 19.3 million cases and 9.96 million deaths in 2020 globally.^{i,ii} Although in the United States, the age-standardized cancer incidence rate in men and cancer mortality in the whole population have been decreasing since 1990s,ⁱⁱⁱ the reverse is the case in developing countries, where the incidence and mortality rates have been exponentially increasing.^{iv} In fact, it was reported that 63% of

cancer-related mortalities occur in developing countries.^v It has been reported that among all cancers, gastrointestinal (GI) cancers have the largest incidence and mortality in many parts of the world.⁶ Lu *et al* in their global assessment of recent trends in gastrointestinal cancers and lifestyle-associated risk factors revealed GI Cancers accounted for about 26.3% of all cases of cancer globally and resulted in 35.4% deaths.⁷ While prevalence of GI cancers is high globally, their epidemiology remains understudied in sub-Saharan Africa, particularly Nigeria.

Gastrointestinal tract (GI) cancers are a group of cancers that can affect the oesophagus, stomach, liver, colon, rectum and anal canal. These cancers are among the most common cancers affecting humans globally.⁶ According to the GLOBOCAN 2020 cancer fact sheet of the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), GI cancers accounted for 25% of new cancer cases (oesophageal- 3.3%, gastric- 6%, liver- 5%, and colorectal- 10.7%) and 31.2% of cancer mortality (oesophageal- 5.5%, gastric- 7.8%, liver- 8.4%, and colorectal- 9.5%) in 2020, which is the largest number of new cases and mortality among all cancer types and a source of significant public health and economic burden for most countries.^{vi} The burden of GI cancers has been increasing globally, due to the growth of aging population, lifestyle changes, smoking, dietary changes, obesity, and increased prevalence of GI infections like helicobacter pylori, hepatitis B and C viruses, especially in the developing countries.^{8,9}

Despite the public health importance of GI cancers, their epidemiology and histopathologic characteristics have not been adequately studied among black Africans. The aim of this study was to examine the demographic and histopathological characteristics of gastrointestinal cancers in Northeastern Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

This was a retrospective review of patients diagnosed with gastrointestinal cancers at six tertiary institutions in Northeastern Nigeria from January 2019 to December 2023. We selected six major tertiary referral centers to get diverse and representative data. The six tertiary healthcare facilities involved in the study are the Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital Azare (FUHSTHA), Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital (ATBUTH) Bauchi, University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital (UMTH), Yobe State University Teaching Hospital (YSUTH), Federal Teaching Hospital (FTH) Gombe, and Federal Medical Centre (FMC) Nguru. These

hospitals are the major tertiary referral centers in the region and offer specialized services in the diagnosis and treatment of cancer.

The inclusion criteria used for this study were as follows; we selected patients of all age groups who had a histological diagnosis of GI cancers (primary cancers of the esophagus, gastric, colorectal, small intestine, liver, and pancreas).

The rationale behind the selection of these GI cancers was that the primary cancers of the esophagus, gastric, colorectal, liver and pancreas were 5 major groups of GI cancers described in GLOBOCAN database.¹⁰ Small intestinal cancers were also included because of their proximity to these sites. The exclusion criteria were as follows, patients with metastatic cancer to the GI system, patients with missing or insufficient information. Figure 1 shows a flow diagram of the patients' selection

Figure 1: Flow Chart of Patient's Selection

Ethical approval was obtained from the Health Research and Ethics Committee of the institutions. Ethical principles and confidentiality were maintained while reviewing the patients' records. Information on the patients' age, gender, organ(s) affected, tumor sub-sites, histological diagnosis, and histological subtype of the tumor were extracted from the tumor registry. The available records of all recruited patients were retrieved, and data was recorded. The data collected was analyzed using SPSS version 26 (IBM SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA). Quantitative variables were expressed as mean and standard deviation. While qualitative data was summarized as frequencies and percentages, and presented as tables, and charts. P values set at ≤ 0.05 were considered significant, at 95% confidence interval.

Results

Demographic Characteristics

A total of 603 cases of GI cancer were retrieved, but 4 patients had metastatic liver cancer from another primary site, and they were excluded. The case

notes of 599 patients were reviewed, 20 patients had inadequate information and so they were also excluded. Data on 579 patients were extracted and analyzed. The incidence of GI cancer was 16.1% (579) out of 3,596 of all patients with GI disease over the period of the study in the six institutions (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Distribution of organs affected by gastrointestinal cancers

The age range of patients was 2 - 92 years, with a median of 52 years and a peak at 50-59 age group. Majority of the patients 441 (76.2%) were 40 years or older and there were 348 (60.1%) males and 231 (39.9%) females, with a male-female ratio of 1.5:1. Table 1 shows the age group and gender cross-tabulation of the studied population. It revealed that there is no statistically significant difference between males and females across age groups, Chi-square (χ^2) = 1.815, $p = 0.936$. The number of cases was noticed to be increasing until it reached its peak in the age group 51-60 years, before it started to decrease.

Histopathological Characteristics

The colorectal region was the most affected site 279 (48.2%), followed by the liver 124 (21.4%), stomach 109 (18.8%), small intestine 32 (5.5%), esophagus 26 (4.5%) and pancreas 9 (1.6%) in descending order (Figure 2).

Table 1: Age Group Distribution and Gender Cross-Tabulation

		GENDER		Total	
		Male	Female		
AGE_GROUP (Years)	< 20	Count	8	8	16
		% within AGE_GROUP	50.0%	50.0%	100.0%
	21-30	Count	38	24	62
		% within AGE_GROUP	61.3%	38.7%	100.0%
	31-40	Count	44	32	76
		% within AGE_GROUP	57.9%	42.1%	100.0%
	41-50	Count	66	42	108
		% within AGE_GROUP	61.1%	38.9%	100.0%
	51-60	Count	85	59	144
		% within AGE_GROUP	59.0%	41.0%	100.0%
	61-70	Count	63	35	98
		% within AGE_GROUP	64.3%	35.7%	100.0%
	> 70	Count	23	17	40
		% within AGE_GROUP	57.5%	42.5%	100.0%
Total		Count	327	217	544
		% within AGE_GROUP	60.1%	39.9%	100.0%

$\chi^2 = 1.815, p = 0.936, \text{ no statistical significant difference}$

Table 2 shows the subsites of intestinal cancers. In the colon ascending, transverse and descending colon 140 (50.2%) were the most affected sub-sites among patients with colorectal cancers. On the other hand, among patients with small intestinal cancers, the jejunum 22 (68.8%) was the most affected site.

Table 3 shows the distribution of histological types of these GI cancers. Overall, epithelial cancers (predominantly adenocarcinoma) were the commonest subtype accounting for 512 (88.4%). Rare types of malignancies observed were lymphomas, melanoma, and small round blue cell tumors including rhabdomyosarcoma, neuroblastoma, and hepatoblastoma.

Table 2: Distribution of Primary Sub-Sites of Intestinal Cancers

Organs	Subsites	Frequency	Percent (%)
Colorectal	#Colon	140	50.2
	Caecum	9	3.2
	Sigmoid	15	5.4
	Rectum	103	36.9
	Anal	12	4.3
Subtotal		279	100
Small intestine			
	Duodenum	3	9.4
	Jejunum	22	68.8
	Ileum	7	21.8
Subtotal		32	100

#ascending, transverse and descending colon

Table 3: Histological Types of Gastrointestinal Cancers

Histological type	Frequency	Percent (%)
Carcinomas (all types)	512	88.4
*GIST	3	0.5
Melanoma	2	0.4
Small round blue cell tumor	10	1.7
Not stated	52	9.0
Total	579	100

*GIST = Gastrointestinal Stromal Tumor

Sub-group categorization revealed that adenocarcinoma was the commonest histological subtype among the colorectal, 216/279 (77.4%) and gastric carcinomas 107/109 (98.2%), while hepatocellular carcinoma 97/124 (78.2%) was the commonest among cancer of the liver. Four of the 9 pancreatic cancers were seen in the head of the pancreas and, the remaining 5 were derived from the pancreatic duct. Squamous cell cancer was the predominant histology type in the esophagus 15/26 (57.7%) whilst adenocarcinoma constituted 7/26 (26.9%) cases.

Discussion

Gastrointestinal cancer is one of the most common cancers globally and the second leading cause of cancer-related mortality.¹¹ It has been a major medical and economic burden worldwide and has the highest incidence and mortality each year.⁶ GI cancers comprised of esophageal, gastric, liver, and colorectal cancers. Among these cancers, esophageal and gastric cancers are more common in developing countries, while colorectal cancer is a more prevalent form of GI malignancy in developed countries.⁶ The distribution and characteristics of GI cancers are poorly described in our environment. In this study, we aimed to describe the demographic and histopathological characteristics of GI malignancies in our environment.

GI cancers are relatively common in our society; in this study, the incidence of GI cancers is 16.1%. This is slightly higher than the incidences reported in other parts of Nigeria. For instance, an incidence of 6.5%, 8.4%, and 15.6% have been reported from different institutions in the Southern part of Nigeria.^{12,13,14} The incidence of 15.6% is closely similar to our findings with comparable demographic characteristics. However, compared with the global incidence, the incidence of GI cancers in this study is lower than the 19.2% reported in the GLOBOCAN study.¹⁵ The disparities in healthcare access and modern equipment may have an impact on the diagnosis and incidence of GI cancers in our environment. Poor access to healthcare services and a lack of modern diagnostic equipment in many of the centers as well as the relatively low index of suspicion may contribute to a lower incidence compared than the global incidence. Cases we found in this study may be just the tip of the iceberg, undiagnosed cases may be found in the community due to a lack of access to healthcare services, a lack of skilled health care personnel, and/or diagnostic equipment to make the definitive diagnosis particularly during the early stages of the malignancies. This is in keeping with a previous report that cancers are generally under-reported in Sub-Saharan Africa.¹⁶ The challenges of

under-diagnosis of cancer in our environment can be addressed through collaborative efforts with national and international partners (like the International Health System Organization), for capacity building, technology transfer, equipment, and knowledge sharing in cancer research for better diagnosis and treatment.

After reviewing the demographic characteristics of patients with GI cancers in this study, the majority of them (71.7%) were older than 40 years, and the most affected age group was 51-60 years. This is comparable to the findings of the Port Harcourt Cancer registry in Nigeria, where they reported that patients in the 50-59 year age group were the most affected with the majority, (63.7%) being older than 45 years of age.¹² The mean age at diagnosis of GI cancers in this study was 50.4±16.0 years. This is similar to the findings of studies conducted in Port Harcourt and Delta in Southern part of Nigeria, that reported mean ages of patients with GI cancers as 51.2±15.8 and 53.4±14.16 years, respectively.^{12,13} However, a multicenter study conducted in France reported a mean age of 63 years among patients with GI cancers.¹⁷ A relatively younger mean age of presentation of GI cancer is found in this study compared to the findings in Europe.¹⁷ The implication of this finding is that GI cancers manifest at an early age in our environment compared to developed countries, and this may affect the actively working population and have a negative impact on the economy. Regarding the age distribution of GI cancers in this study, no specific risk factors have been identified as triggers for the early manifestation of these cancers in our environment. However, early intervention and risk stratification strategies can be tailored toward addressing general risk factors like limiting smoking and alcohol consumption in younger individuals. This study also revealed a slight male predominance with a male-female ratio of 1.5:1. This agrees with the findings from previous studies in Nigeria,¹² and in Europe,¹⁷ but in variance with another study that reported an equal gender distribution.¹³

It has been observed that the incidence of GI cancers is rising in our environment, and which has been attributed to diet and some environmental factors.¹⁸ Increased intake of low fiber diet such as fast-food, roasted meat, or fish may be implicated. Many households used smoke or deep-fried meat and fish for preservation and consumption, due to a lack of good electricity to refrigerate and preserve the meat in our environment. Smoked fish, and meat have been shown to contain high levels of heterocyclic amines and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

(PAHs) (e.g. benzopyrene), which have been identified as human carcinogens.^{19,20} In recent times, tobacco consumption has increased in many developing countries while decreasing in developed countries.²¹ Nigeria is one of the highest tobacco consumers worldwide, and young adults are increasingly taking up this smoking habit in Northeastern Nigeria, thereby increasing their susceptibility and risk of GI cancers.²² Furthermore, PAHs has been identified as one of the major carcinogens in cigarette smoke. Other environmental pollutants, such as vehicle exhausts, and diesel-generator exhausts, also release excessive PAHs and many toxins into our environment, due to increased demand for transportation and household electricity, thereby increasing the risk of GI cancers.²³ The contribution of environmental pollution as a risk factor for GI cancer can be prevented through green-energy and environmental sustainability programs.

Socio-economic variables can also influence the incidence of GI cancers in our environment. Northeastern Nigeria is one of the economically less developed regions in Nigeria, coupled with the fact that the region has suffered a prolonged period of humanitarian crises with a large number of internally displaced persons in camps in different areas.²⁴ The available healthcare facilities focus their attention on solving the humanitarian crises, emerging infectious disease outbreaks like Lassa fever, cerebrospinal meningitis, cholera as well as COVID-19 pandemic. This hampered the diagnosis and treatment of cancer in the region. Other barriers to accessing specialized cancer care and treatment for patients with cancer in Northeastern Nigeria include traditional beliefs, cultural ideologies, religious differences and ignorance. For instance, some traditional people believe that cancer is not treatable in the hospital, and some believe injections are contraindicated and worsens the condition of the patient. Some believe that cancer usually results from contact with the evil spirit in the bush or forest, linked to the Hausa language terminology "daji".²⁵ The combination of these factors prevents early diagnosis and treatment, and may influence health-seeking behaviors and treatment adherence among patients with GI cancers in our environment. These challenges can be addressed through collaborative multidisciplinary efforts, with psychologists, nurses, caregivers, social influencers, opinion shapers and humanitarian workers. Public health campaigns and education initiatives will also help in raising awareness and promoting strategies to address these psychosocial barriers.

Regarding the histopathological characteristics, colorectal cancer constituted the majority of GI cancers in this study, followed by liver and gastric cancers. This is similar to the report by Obiorah and Ray-Offor from Nigeria, where colorectal cancer constituted the majority of GI cancers in their study.¹² Similarly, a study conducted in France reported that the colorectal cancer was the commonest type of GI cancer, but in contrast to this study, the second and third common types were pancreatic and gastric cancer, respectively.¹⁷ The distribution of histological types of GI cancers in this study showed that colorectal adenocarcinoma was the commonest, followed by gastric adenocarcinoma and hepatocellular carcinoma. This is in agreement with the findings from a Nigerian study that reported adenocarcinoma as being the most common histological type of colorectal and gastric cancers in their population.¹³ Another study in our environment also reported that adenocarcinoma is the most common histological variant of colorectal cancers, accounting for 96-98% of malignant colorectal tumors.¹² The trend of gastric cancers in this study is similar to the findings of researchers in Iran, who reported that the most common histological type of gastric cancer was adenocarcinoma.^{26,27} Since adenocarcinoma has been the most predominant histological type in our setting, screening and early diagnostic strategies should be instituted in order to improve diagnosis, optimal treatment, and overall patient survival. In this setting, there are a lot of opportunities for screening for GI cancers. Since these cancers initially present with vague symptoms, it is usually difficult to differentiate the cancers from other benign GI diseases until a specific investigation is performed. The specific screening investigations include fecal occult blood test (FOBT), fecal immunochemical testing, etc. Screening colonoscopy, sigmoidoscopy, and upper GI endoscopy are also recommended for individuals with worrisome symptoms to detect and take a biopsy. Some of the challenges for screening and diagnosis of GI cancer in our environment include lack of genetic testing, and a lack of universal guidelines for patients requiring screening endoscopy as it is obtainable elsewhere. For instance, the European Society of Gastrointestinal Endoscopy position statement recommends that: 1. Endoscopic screening for gastric cancer should be performed to individuals older than 40 years. 2. For colorectal cancer, population-based screening is recommended (by doing fecal immunochemical testing) targeting all individuals aged 50-75 years, regardless of the

gender.²⁸ Considering these recommendations, unique age targeted screening of GI cancers can be achieved in Northeastern Nigeria through fecal immunohistochemical testing, upper and lower GI endoscopies, etc. Facilities for the screening should be provided by the government, and other non-government actors. Equally important, the government should be guided for proper allocation of healthcare resources and funding priorities for cancer research and treatment in Northeastern Nigeria. There should be adequate facilities to mount robust screening, diagnostic, and treatment cancer centers in the region.

Most of the patients with liver cancer in this study were diagnosed with hepatocellular carcinoma (78.2%). The cases of liver cancer reported in this study may be an underestimation of the true burden of the disease, because many of the cases of liver cancer present at an advanced stage when biopsy may not be possible, so we rely on clinical and radiological diagnosis.²⁹ The increased cases of hepatocellular carcinoma in our environment may be attributed to Hepatitis B and C virus infection. Hepatitis B virus (HBV) has been strongly implicated in the carcinogenesis of hepatocellular carcinoma.³⁰ A comprehensive awareness, screening and linkage to care will be a key approach in addressing most of the hepatitis B and, hepatitis C related hepatocellular carcinoma. Understanding this concept is very important in the prevention strategy, because public health interventions such as routine HBV immunization will go a long way in curtailing this disease. Public health campaigns and education initiatives aimed at raising awareness about the modes of transmission of hepatitis B and hepatitis C viruses, such as unsafe blood transfusion, faeco-oral transmission, and unprotected sex will help in the prevention of these diseases. Public health campaigns should be targeted at both males and females. But the campaign is easier for males in our environment because of the cultural barriers; females are less accessible than males.

From the findings of this study, which is in consonance with published literature, it is obvious that there are a lot of gaps in cancer research in our environment, ranging from the identification of risk factors, treatment strategies, prognosis, and outcome of treatment. Therefore, further studies are required; to elucidate the modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors, to identify any genetic basis, and to determine the best therapeutic option for the treatment of GI malignancies. Prospective studies, interventional research, or clinical trials may be required to fill in those knowledge gaps. But there

are ethical and cultural sensitivities issues associated with conducting cancer research and implementing clinical trials in Northeastern Nigeria, due to misconceptions, traditional beliefs, and ignorance. These challenges can be addressed through effective high level advocacy campaigns and public awareness.

Some of the limitations of this study include the retrospective nature of the research, and there are a few missing data especially on the prognosis and outcome of GI cancers as many never came back for follow-up. This problem can be overcome by the establishment of a regional cancer registry and surveillance system that will help in monitoring the incidence, treatment monitoring, and outcome of GI cancer over time in Northeastern Nigeria.

In summary, this study highlighted the demographic and histopathological characteristics of GI cancers in Northeastern Nigeria. The findings of this study can be extrapolated to inform policy decisions and healthcare planning at the state, regional and national level. However, these findings may not be generalized due to some limitations such as our inability to follow-up the patients, to find out the treatment progression, the outcome and prognosis of the disease. This study also considered only histologically diagnosed cancer cases, and cases diagnosed using clinical, imaging, or other laboratory modalities may have been missed. This study may under-represent the true incidence nature of GI cancers in our environment. We, therefore, advocate for further studies that will investigate the true prevalence and incidence of GI cancers in our environment.

Conclusion

This study revealed that the incidence of GI cancers in Northeastern Nigeria was 16.1%. The incidence is increasing with age, reaching a peak at the age of 51-60 years, with a male preponderance. The most common site affected was the colorectal region, followed by the liver and stomach. Colorectal adenocarcinoma, gastric adenocarcinoma, and hepatocellular carcinoma are the most common histological subtypes. Therefore, further studies are recommended to examine the modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors, and to identify any genetic basis of colorectal adenocarcinoma and other GI cancers in our environment.

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